

Sigmoid Vaginoplasty In Vaginal Agenesis With History Of Two Times Vaginal Drainage Surgery

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Abstract

Introduction: vaginal agenesis with functional uterus is a rare condition usually presents in puberty with a pain in the abdomen. Vaginal agenesis can be managed with non-operative and operative surgery. Sigmoid colon vaginoplasty is a technique that is known to produce an excellent and functional vagina. Methods: case examination and tracing medical record. Results: a nineteenth years old female POAO present with abdominal pain and history of two times vaginal drainage surgery. From the MRI examination reveal that there is a narrow vagina with 0.4 cm in caliber and 3.2 cm in length and there also dilatation of uterus cavity filled with hematometra. Discussion: there are various number of techniques that can be used for management of vaginal agenesis. One of the surgical techniques that can be used in management of vaginal agenesis is sigmoid colon vaginoplasty. Surgical procedure then performed in this patient to produce a neovagina for both draining menstrual blood in case with functional uterus and future sexual activity. Sigmoid colon vaginoplasty are selected for its excellence in produce a well-functioning neovagina. Conclusion: vaginal agenesis with functional uterus is a rare condition. Patient usually came in puberty with abdominal pain that cause from the obstructed menstrual blood in the uterus. Sigmoid colon vaginoplasty was a surgical procedure that known to give satisfactory results in patient with vaginal agenesis. Postoperative follow up is a must to evaluate the function of patient neovagina.

Introduction

Vaginal agenesis is an uncommon congenital anomaly, occurring in approximately 1 in 4,000 to 10,000 females, it involves the complete or partial absence of the uterus, vagina, or both. Uterine remnant may be present or there may be a uterus in the form of uterine horn, with or without an endometrial cavity. The vagina can be either a short canal or a dimple under the urethra. Vaginal agenesis usually can be detected in post pubertal girls as primary amenorrhea, XX karyotype, and normally functioning ovaries. If the case is an isolated anomaly, it is commonly referred to as the Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome (Both *et.al.*, 2018; Committee on Adolescent Health Care, 2018).

The neovaginal surgical procedure is a procedure that can manage cases of vaginal agenesis, this surgery aims to create the vaginal canal that can function in penile penetration during sexual activity, as well as other function of menstrual blood outflow in cases with the functional uterus. Until now, there is no single neovaginal surgical technique that was agreed by the expert to manage this diagnosis. Sigmoid colon vaginoplasty is one kind of surgical procedure that can be used for treating patient with vaginal agenesis. This surgery was expected to produce a vagina that could function for life for the patient (Pangastutiet.al., 2020).

Method

Starting with a case search, then an examination is carried out according to the procedure. Completeness of data obtained from medical record.

Results and Discussion

Results

Eighteen years old female POAO, presented with abdominal pain especially during menstruation, with history of two times surgery. The menarche happens when she was 12 years old at 2015, after the first surgery in the form of vaginal drainage as well as laparotomy right salpingoophorocystectomy as indicated by a right chocolate cyst. This surgical vaginal drainage was followed by the insertion of an intravaginal catheter balloon for one month to

maintain patency of the vaginal canal. After this surgery her cycles were regular and the menstruation usually lasted 4-5 days with severe dysmenorrhea.

The complaints return at 2016, patient said that she had not menstruate for about a month follows with abdominal cramps. She was taken to another hospital and diagnosed with appendicitis. The surgeon intended to perform appendectomy, but when the surgery was done, the diagnosis of right chocolate cyst was confirmed and right salpingoophorocystectomy was performed. The surgeon was also performed vaginal drainage but the pain persisted in the months after the surgery. Patient was then referred to the gynecologist who then performed drainage and laminaria insertion. Before she was brought to the tertiary hospital, another gynecologist had tried a cross incision to the patient but couldn't penetrate through hematometra.

On physical examination, there is no abdominal distention. Abdomen was tender and there was pain at the suprapubic area. Rectal examination was performed and a uterine structure was found at the anterior extraluminary side of the rectum about 6 cm from the anus. From the examination of the external genitalia, the results were within normal limits. Laboratory examination of a complete blood count also conducted for the patient and the results was within normal limits.

Radiological examination was performed in this case. In her first admission, upper lower abdominal ultrasound examination was conducted, the result is a suspected hematosalpinx at parametrium sinistra with no other anomalies found. Magnetic Resonance Imaging examination reveal that there was a narrow vagina with 0.4 cm in caliber and 3.2 cm in length and there also dilatation of uterus cavity filled with hematometra, both kidney were normal. Contrast x-rays was also conducted with results in the abdomen, the examination found that no kidney stones visualized, both kidney and ureter were normal. Colon in loop examination was also performed and no abnormalities were found.

In these case, sigmoid colon vaginoplasty or sigmoid vaginoplasty was selected as the procedure to form the neovagina for the patient. During the 7 hours operation, it was found that there is an enlargement of the uterus size with an adhesion to the colon in posterior side and to the abdominal wall in the lateral side.

Figure 1. Left ovary and fallopian tube (blue arrow)

There's an endometriosis nodules at the anterior and posterior of uterine corpus and fundus, fulguration was performed and the sample was sent to pathological anatomy laboratorium. There was no right tube and right ovary. There is a narrowing of the left tube near the uterus, normal fimbriae, and normal left ovary. The rectovesical space was identified by performing a gradual dilation using a number of Hegar's dilators through the defect from the two previous drainage procedure. Then, the hematometra can be drained out of approximately 250 ml. The diameter of rectovesical space is widened until it reaches diameter 3-4 cm. Sigmoid graft with \pm 20 cm in length obtained from the digestive surgeon who performed resection and end-to-end anastomosis of the sigmoid colon. Next the sigmoid graft is placed in the rectovesical space that has been prepared, antiperistaltically in a 180degree clockwise direction. Total blood loss during the surgery was approximately 900 ml and patient received a transfusion of 500 ml packed red blood cell.

Figure 2. Sigmoid graft for the vaginoplasty

Figure 3. Longitudinal incision of lower part of the uterus through the cervix

Patient then monitored for the postsurgery condition. She was in stable condition. Patient also get mobilized gradually until she can walk. There is no significant complaint after the surgery is performed. Patient then discharged 10 days after the surgery.

Discussion

Vaginal agenesis is a rare condition with an incidence ranging from 1 in 4000 to 1 in 10.000 females. The most common etiology is Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser (MRKH). Syndrome or Mullerian agenesis which is described as congenital absence of uterus and vagina in an individual with normal female genotype, normal secondary sexual characteristic and normal ovaries (Beksac*et.al.*, 2011). The cause is not fully understood, but a failure in the canalization of the Mullerian ducts in embryologic phase of the development of the female fetus is thought to be the main mechanism (Both *et.al.*, 2018).

The Müllerian malformation manifests with various phenotypes due to the variance of developmental defects in the female genitourinary tract. Both cervicovaginal agenesis and vaginal agenesis or cervical atresia are thought to originate with developmental defects of the Müllerian tubercle (Minami *et.al.*, 2019). The vaginal canal is markedly shortened and may appear as a dimple below the urethra. The ovaries, given their separate embryologic source, are typically normal in structure and function, though they may be found in an atypical location (Committee on Adolescent Health Care, 2018).

The external genitalia appear to be normal and the patient typically have a normal reproductive function and reach puberty showing normal signs of thelarche and pubarche. Patient usually seeks medical help with primary amenorrhea during adolescence. In this situation, Müllerian aplasia is the most probable diagnosis (Herlin*et.al.*, 2020). In some cases like in this patient, the uterus may be extremely rudimentary and have a functioning endometrium which made the patient present with the abdominal pain, owing to progressive blood congestion in the uterine cavity (Creatsas&Deligeoroglou, 2010).

There are various number of techniques that can be used for management of vaginal agenesis, surgically or non-surgically. Surgical vaginoplasty is divided into following categories; (1) creation of perineal pouch (Williams vaginoplasty and subsequent modification) (2) pressure method (Vecchiotti procedure) and (3) lining a neovaginal space. At present, there is no consensus yet in the literature regarding the best surgical technique to provide the best functional outcome and sexual satisfaction(Handaya*et.al.*, 2020).

One of the techniques that can be used in management of vaginal agenesis is sigmoid colon vaginoplasty. The procedure was chosen in this case because it can create an excellent and aesthetically vaginal canal with a good length that can function both in sexual activity considering the patient who is still in her reproductive age and also as an access of menstrual blood outflow tract for the patient with functional uterus(Pangastuti*et.al.*, 2020). There is no need to perform regular dilatation which made the patient inconvenient and also the sigmoid itself could provide natural lubrication, when performed before puberty, the sigmoid graft can grow with the child, also there is minimal risk of stenosis(Handaya*et.al.*, 2020). Intraoperative complications are rare, postoperative complication include ileus, wound infection, pelvic hematoma, urinary tract infection, abscess, and necrosis, which didn't happen in this case.

During surgery, the operator discovered multiple adhesion from the uterus to the colon and vice versa. This could be the result from her past surgery. One thing that surgeons always have to be aware of is when they have to perform surgery in cases with a history of previous surgery, especially a history of surgery in the genital area and reproductive organs. The risk of injury when opening the adhesive must be communicated well in advance. The risk of additional hours of surgery as well as infection and bleeding must also be prepared for prevention

before surgery. Adhesions that are often found in this case can then be removed quickly so that the duration of the surgery is more efficient. It can avoid an increase in the amount of bleeding and the risk of further infection. After the patient can be discharged, an evaluation should be carried out to assess the patient's next condition. It must be ensured that the surgical wound heals well, the sigmoid graft can function as a neovagina in the long term of the patient's life. In the reported case there was no signs of infection or stenosis during this healing phase. The examination of her neovaginal function is very important to achieve the goal of adequate monthly menstrual blood drainage.

Long term, if the patient is married, evaluation can be made of this neovaginal function in relation to sexual activity, especially for the purpose of sexual penetration. To examine the patient during sexual function follow up, we could use Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI) questionnaire. FSFI is a multidimensional questions that can show female sexual function. It's consisted of 6 domains, which is; sexual desire, sexual arousal, lubrication, orgasm, sexual satisfaction, and pain (Pangastuti *et al.*, 2019). For the best of the results, we could evaluate the patient starting every week for a month, once in a month for 3 months, and twice a year for the following years (Pangastuti *et al.*, 2020).

Conclusion

Vaginal agenesis is a rare condition with an incidence of 1:4000 to 1:10.000 as a result of failure in canalization during Mullerian period. In cases with functional uterus, patient usually came in puberty with abdominal pain that cause from the obstructed menstrual blood in the uterus. Sigmoid colon vaginoplasty was a surgical procedure that known to give satisfactory results in patient with vaginal agenesis. There were no significant complaints after surgery, the function of neovagina to drain menstrual blood was good, the appearance of vaginal cosmetics was also satisfactory. Evaluation needs to be done periodically to always monitor this neovagina condition.

Recommendations

A complete and thorough evaluation should be carried out before performing any surgical procedure as a treatment in cases of vaginal agenesis especially with a functional uterus, to avoid the risk of repeated surgery with all the consequences.

Sigmoid vaginoplasty is one of the surgical procedures that can be chosen for the management of vaginal agenesis cases with a functional uterus, because it can drain menstrual blood, which can function throughout the patient's life. This procedure is also useful if the patient will have sexual activity in the future, has a good aesthetic appearance so that it can be well received by patients.

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